

REHABILITATION: MOBILITY, EXERCISE & SPORTS

"The influence of force and change in muscle length on the incidence of spasticity in the upper extremity during Boccia ball throwing in elite Boccia players"

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PURPOSE: The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of force and change in muscle length on the incidence of spasticity in the upper extremity during boccia.

METHODS: Muscle activity of six arm muscles of five participants was measured with electromyography (EMG) during nine different underhand throwing conditions. These nine conditions consisted of three different levels of force that had to be exerted with three different changes in muscle length during the throw. Based on the underhand throwing technique, the muscle activity of two antagonist muscles in the shoulder, two in the upper arm and two in the forearm were measured. The EMG data were used to identify spasms during throwing in boccia athletes with cerebral palsy.

RESULTS: We observed significantly more spasms in the conditions where the range of motion of the arm before the throw is greater compared to the conditions where the range of motion is decreased ($p = 0.035$) in the forearm. Furthermore, spasticity is more frequently present in the forearm compared to the shoulder and upper arm muscles.

CONCLUSIONS: The results seem to indicate that the amount of force that has to be exerted does not influence the incidence of spasticity, whereas change in muscle length during the throw does. It is also evident that spasticity is more frequently present in the forearm compared to the shoulder and upper arm muscles in athletes with cerebral palsy during boccia throwing.